

LEXICAL MEANS OF TEMPORARY RELATIONSHIPS IN THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the main grammatical means of the category of time in the Russian and Uzbek languages on the basis of journalistic texts. As a result of the analysis, it was revealed that aspectual forms as grammatical means of expressing temporal relations can express both actual and irrelevant meanings relative to the grammatical reference point. Participles can express both relative and absolute time.

Time is an important attribute of the category of being and at the same time it is likened to being in many aspects of its manifestations. In everyday life we feel the passage of time and the experience of it is connected with the experience of our own "I", with the experience of our own existence.

In the 70-80s. In the 20th century, linguists became interested in the problem of updating the category of time in language. The study of language time is one of the most developed topics in modern linguistics. Some scientists single out the category of time as a text -forming one, for example, I.R. Galperin speaks of the category of time as "the unity of the continuum, retrospection and propection" [1, p. 106]. A.V. Bondarko notes "a complex of semantic categories reflecting various aspects of the concept of time. This complex includes the categories of temporality, aspectuality, temporal localization and temporal order" [2, p. 29]. E.V. Tarasova writes that "temporality is a category of a

higher rank, which subjugates grammatical time as one of the strategies used in natural language to reflect time by linguistic means" [3, p. 36]. Time is one of the most important categories of human existence, which has always aroused the interest of researchers in various fields of knowledge, including linguists. The language category of time is a complex phenomenon of linguistics, which has different approaches to study and is expressed using the means of different levels of the language system.

The verb, as a grammatical means of expressing time, is represented in Russian and Uzbek not only by the category of grammatical tense, but also by the category of aspect. The morphological category of time is built on the basis of the opposition of various types of tense forms of the verb. Each of the forms opposed to each other is characterized by special grammatical time markers. These markers include, firstly, affixes (for example, the suffix of past tense forms: Some things were created during the war years in the Far East, for example,

tunics of the 1943 model), and secondly, the types of stems to which these affixes are attached. Present tense forms are characterized by the presence of special endings with the meaning of person and number, which are adjacent to the basis of the present tense of imperfective verbs, for example : Annunciation is invited to sing "The Last Battle" online, and zero representation of the existential verb, for example: He is the winner of the most prestigious international competitions in Russia, Spain, Italy, France and the USA. Forms of perfective verbs of the future simple tense are also formed with the help of personal endings attached to the stem of perfective verbs, for example: An artistic ensemble of radio and TV from Guangdong province will perform in Blagoveshchensk . But in the Uzbek language you cannot meet such a phenomenon, since in the Uzbek language there are no genders at the personal ending of the verb. Contrasted with all other forms of time, the forms of the future complex - as analytical synthetic; these forms have a special time marker - an existential link to be, for example : Applications for participation in the celebration of the city's day will be accepted until July 1. The categorical meanings of tense forms as an orientation are aimed at a single starting point - a grammatical reference point. This concept is abstract and is generally perceived either as the moment of speaking, or as any other moment relative to which the time of action at the moment of speaking is determined. Semantically, grammatical forms have "differential signs of simultaneity, precedence or following in relation to the moment of speech or another reference point" [1, p. 84]. It is important to note that, depending on the conditions of the context, the verb is able to represent

other temporary meanings, thus being in its irrelevant meaning relative to the moment of speaking. For example, the forms of the present tense can act in the meaning of the past, future and present timeless. A similar situation, but less common, occurs in the forms of the future tense: the future irrelevant can express the semantics of the present timeless.

Consider the following examples of present imperfective verb forms: No, we are talking purely about the promotion of cinema; "It felt like a tour,"

- the spectator Irina notices and asks for more time to "think up", taking the bubbling aftertaste home. In the given examples, the highlighted imperfective verbs express the semantics of the simultaneity of the action with the moment of speaking and act in their main temporal meaning of the present actual. It must be said that in journalistic texts the present topical is extremely rare. These examples are taken from interviews - one of the few genres of journalism where you can find an action that takes place simultaneously with the moment of speaking. Another variant of the present irrelevant tense can be the present potential. This meaning is mainly expressed by verbs that "express the ability, the ability of the subject to perform the actions they denote" [3, p. eighteen]. Let's look at some examples: Elvira Gabaraeva , the soloist of the pop -jazz orchestra " AmurJazzBand ", sings beautifully in Chinese; Do you dance yourself? Or just teach others? Highlighted word forms denote the ability to do something in general, and not at the moment of speech.

In addition, as a variety of this irrelevant, one can consider the present presentation, which is presented most often in scripts, reviews, and annotations. For example : The

action of the next part of the Bond series takes place in Jamaica. The protagonist's quiet rest is violated by his friend, who works for the CIA. He asks Bond to help retrieve the stolen property, which proves to be a difficult task. In this passage, the highlighted forms of the present tense are in a weak position and appear in an indirect temporal meaning.

Another type of irrelevant meaning of the present tense is the present of the upcoming action, which in the linguistic literature is often called "the present of the planned future" [4, p. 155]. A.M. Peshkovsky described it as follows: "The present instead of the future for the depiction of facts imagined in the future, as if already occurring at the moment of the very presentation of them to oneself" [5, p. 209]. The specific semantics of this type limits the range of verbs that are used in this sense. Usually these are verbs of movement. Let's look at some examples: Chaif goes to Blagoveshchensk ; The Far Eastern Feature Film Festival "Point of Return 2019" is coming to Blagoveshchensk.

Thus, the form of the imperfective present tense verb in Russian and Uzbek, depending on the conditions of the context, can express the actual and irrelevant meanings of time. The position of the types of temporary forms, like I will explain, I will show, is debatable in linguistics. "From the problems of verb tense relations with other grammatical categories, - notes A.V. Bondarko, - one of the most complex "knots" of species-temporal relations stands out - the collision of the present tense and the perfect form" [1, p. 4]. Traditionally, such forms are referred to as the future simple or future perfect form. A. V. Bondarko considers such forms as semantically dual, polysemantic. Let's look at some examples:

I don't understand why this is surprising? - Irina Medvedeva was perplexed; I can't imagine, I don't know anyone who would have learned ... In the first sentence, the highlighted verb is in a strong position in the context and has the meaning of a real actual action that takes place simultaneously with the moment of speaking. In the second example, the highlighted phraseological unit expresses the impossibility of performing an action that is relevant for the moment of speaking. The most common temporal meaning of the future perfect form is the meaning of the actual future action. Let's look at examples: Chaif will perform in Blagoveshchensk; Museum visitors will get acquainted with the work of the famous Amur artist. In these examples, the highlighted verbs are in the meaning of following the moment of speaking, which is relevant for them.

The form of the future imperfect tense is unambiguous, i.e. always stands inside the context in a strong position and expresses the semantics of the future actual. For example : Exhibitions of paintings with augmented reality will appear more and more often in Blagoveshchensk; The Amur Regional Drama Theater will post videos of its performances on the main page of the official website. The forms of the verbs in the above sentences express the actual time value relative to the moment of speaking.

The meaning of the past tense form is limited by the past tense plan. In other words, the forms of the past tense are characterized by a strong position in the context and the realization of the main temporal meaning that is relevant to the moment of speaking. The presented examples clearly illustrate this fact: The training took place remotely; Lyubov Uspenskaya greeted from the stage in

Blagoveshchensk, Primorsky Krai; The first issue took place a week before the start of the fateful events; For the first time, the text of the song "The Last Fight" was heard in the final film of the epic film "Liberation". In the examples given, the highlighted imperfective and perfective verbs express their basic meaning of precedence, because they are in a strong position.

The linguistic literature describes various views on the characteristics of the category of participle time. Some researchers believe that participles can only express relative time, i.e. in relation to the time of the verb-predicate (И.И. Буланин) , others - that participial forms can have the meanings of both relative and absolute time (A. V. Bondarko, M. A. Shelyakin , etc.) . Consider examples: An exhibition dedicated to World Radio Day was opened there - Wed: an exhibition was opened that was timed to coincide with World Radio Day; The Amur Regional Scientific Library will hold a series

of intellectual games dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the Victory in the Great Patriotic War - Wed: the library will hold a series of games dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the Victory. In examples, participles express the past relative tense with the meaning of precedence in relation to the action of the verb-predicate.

Thus, aspectual forms of verbs and participles in Russian and Uzbek languages are the main grammatical means of expressing temporality in Russian. Aspective forms of the verb are able to act in the actual meaning relative to the moment of speaking and represent their main meanings: precedence, simultaneity, following. Depending on the conditions of the context, the verb may be in a weak position and express other temporary meanings, thus being in its irrelevant meaning relative to the moment of speaking. Participle forms are capable of expressing both relative and absolute time.

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